

Dendrochronological analysis of timbers from two shipwrecks found at Myttingeviken, Stockholm.

by

Aoife Daly.

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Samples from two shipwrecks found at Myttingeviken, Stockholm, were submitted for dendrochronological analysis, to determine their date and provenance. The wrecks are suspected to be two naval ships *Neptunus* and *Tu Löver*, captured from the Danish fleet in 1644 at the battle of Femern. The results of the dendrochronological analysis are described in this report.

Fig. 1. Myttingeviken, Stockholm. The chronological position of the dated samples from the two ships.

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Neptunus

Neptunus was captured by the Swedes, from the Danish Navy, in 1644 (Glete 2010), so she must be older than this. Glete lists *Neptunus* as converted to a fireship in 1657. Eleven samples are from *Neptunus*. All the samples from the wreck are oak (*Quercus* sp.) and of these, eight are dated.

Two of the dated samples are from hull planks. Sample p3 (Z2950019) contains 79 tree-rings, all heartwood. This sample is from a tree felled after AD 1550. Sample P5 (Z2950059) contains 129 tree-rings, all heartwood. This sample is from a tree felled after AD 1555.

Two of the dated samples are from frames. Sample P11 (Z295008a) contains 94 tree-rings (only heartwood) and is from a tree felled after AD 1553. Sample P12 (Z295010a) contains 51 tree-rings, only heartwood. It is from a tree felled after AD 1611.

A sample from a beam (P8, Z2950069) contains 91 tree-rings, all heartwood. This beam is from a tree felled after AD 1625.

A sample from a deck beam (P4, Z295004a) contains 81 tree-rings all heartwood and is from a tree felled after AD 1624.

Finally, two samples are from knees in the ship. Sample P10 (Z2950029) contains 144 tree-rings, including four sapwood rings. This knee is from a tree felled AD 1624-39. Sample P1 (Z295003a) contains 114 tree-rings, including 22 sapwood rings. This knee is from a tree felled AD 1629-36.

If it is assumed that all the dated samples are from trees felled at the same time, then this felling took place around AD 1629-36 (indicated with sky-blue shading in fig. 1).

Two samples from *Neptunus*, P6 and P9, could not be dated. They contain 65 and 53 tree-rings respectively.

	Z296004a p19	Z2960059 p16	Z296002a p13	Z295003a p1	Z295004a p4	Z295010a p12	Z2950019 p3	Z2950069 p8	Z2950029 p10	Z2960019 p15	Z296006a p18	Z2950059 p5	Z295008a p11
Z296004a p19	*	1.03	1.29	-	1.44	0.51	-	2.00	-	0.12	-	-	0.7
Z2960059 p16	1.03	*	3.48	0.29	\	\	1.85	0.76	0.21	0.03	2.18	2.02	1.78
Z296002a p13	1.29	3.48	*	2.24	4.02	0.01	2.58	0.7	0.75	1.94	1.71	1.42	1.69
Z295003a p1	-	0.29	2.24	*	3.29	1.15	1.57	1.05	2.34	2.46	-	0.89	0.96
Z295004a p4	1.44	\	4.02	3.29	*	3.29	\	1.05	1.32	1.61	\	\	\
Z295010a p12	0.51	\	0.01	1.15	3.29	*	\	1.23	1.24	2.78	\	\	\
Z2950019 p3	-	1.85	2.58	1.57	\	\	*	\	2.64	2.47	2.59	1.8	1.64
Z2950069 p8	2.00	0.76	0.7	1.05	1.05	1.23	\	*	1.34	2.75	0.49	3.07	\
Z2950029 p10	-	0.21	0.75	2.34	1.32	1.24	2.64	1.34	*	5.25	1.97	3.3	1.56
Z2960019 p15	0.12	0.03	1.94	2.46	1.61	2.78	2.47	2.75	5.25	*	0.52	1.39	1.3
Z296006a p18	-	2.18	1.71	-	\	\	2.59	0.49	1.97	0.52	*	3.38	2.59
Z2950059 p5	-	2.02	1.42	0.89	\	\	1.8	3.07	3.3	1.39	3.38	*	4.16
Z295008a p11	0.7	1.78	1.69	0.96	\	\	1.64	\	1.56	1.3	2.59	4.16	*

Table 1. Myttingeviken, Stockholm. Result of the correlations (*t*-value) between the tree-ring curves from the dated samples with each other. Blue highlights the dates samples from *Neptunus*, brown are those from *To Löver*.

Provenance *Neptunus*

No highly significant correlations appear between the dated samples from *Neptunus* at their dated position (see table 1). The samples are dating independently, and the highest correlations that are achieved for each tree-ring curve are shown in tables 2 to 9 below. Some timbers are matching best with northern Germany, some with The Netherlands, others again with Danish tree-ring datasets. Generally, these results indicate that the ship was built of oak from a wide range of sources. Thus, it is very difficult to suggest from the dendrochronological analysis alone, where *Neptunus* might have been built.

A post associated with the *Neptunus* wreck (P2, Z295101a) is pine (*Pinus* sp.), and it contains 53 tree-rings. This sample could not be dated.

Filenames	-	-	Z2950019 p3	
-	start	dates	AD1456	
-	dates	end	AD1534	
H11C0M01	AD1443	AD1613	7.75	Wahlstorf. Herrenha 6 timbers (Hamburg Uni revised Daly 2007a)
H1372M01	AD1409	AD1536	6.88	Norderst. Haus 6 timbers (Hamburg Uni revised Daly 2007a)
H118TM01	AD1404	AD1605	6.54	Suelfeld Kirche 14 timbers (Hamburg Uni revised Daly 2007a)
H11I0M01	AD1423	AD1541	6.43	HL Engelswisch 22 4 timbers (Hamburg Uni revised Daly 2007a)
G370HZ01	AD1426	AD1617	6.26	Oldenburg 31 timbers (Göttingen Uni revised Daly 2007a)
CD50PZ02	AD1458	AD1618	6.22	Varns Klokkehus 3 timbers (Nationalmuseet revised Daly 2007a)
H12BVM01	AD1454	AD1557	6.19	Hohenhorst Wildkoppe 2 timbers (Hamburg Uni revised Daly 2007a)
9M456781	109BC	AD1986	6.09	Jylland/Fyn (Nationalmuseet)
H11GSM01	AD1397	AD1543	6.01	HL Engelsgrube 31 8 timbers (Hamburg Uni revised Daly 2007a)
DM100003	AD436	AD1968	5.91	Schleswig-Holstein (Hamburg Uni)
HO14ZF01	AD1387	AD1661	5.80	Gadebusch Schloss 17 timbers (Hamburg Uni revised Daly 2007a)
HO32VM02	AD1474	AD1672	5.80	Zarrentin Kirche 18 timbers (Hamburg Uni revised Daly 2007a)
G350OZ01	AD1353	AD1584	5.58	Soltau 7 timbers (Göttingen Uni revised Daly 2007a)
H11KLM01	AD1385	AD1589	5.57	HL Mengstr. 44 18 timbers (Hamburg Uni revised Daly 2007a)
DM200001	AD1082	AD1972	5.51	Nieders. Kuestenraum (Göttingen Uni)
H11KPM01	AD1422	AD1557	5.51	HL Mengstrasse 23 3 timbers (Hamburg Uni revised Daly 2007a)
DM100006end	AD1330	AD1650	5.50	Lübeck (Hamburg Uni)
H127BM01	AD1453	AD1600	5.50	Krempe altes Rathaus 10 timbers (Hamburg Uni revised Daly 2007a)

Table 2. Myttingeviken, Stockholm. Result of the correlation between the tree-ring curve from plank sample p3 (Z2950019) from *Neptunus* and diverse site and master chronologies. The source of the chronologies is given. The grey tone highlights the high *t*-values.

Filenames	-	-	Z2950059 p5	
-	start	dates	AD1411	
-	dates	end	AD1539	
nlwf1040	AD1040	AD1972	7.99	Nederland. Westfalen (H.Tisje 1987 unpubl)
TWWFMD01	AD1216	AD1660	7.77	NL Twente/Westfalen 51 trees (Dominguez Delmas unpubl)
nlmidden	AD1023	AD1666	7.69	Mid Netherlands (Jansma pers comm)
00654m01	AD1380	AD1581	7.63	Copenhagen B&W Wreck 4 (Daly 1997d)
00651m08low	AD1418	AD1597	7.51	B&W1 lengthening 7 timbers (Daly 2007a)
sudeutoref2	AD418	AD1987	6.14	S Deuts REF2 (Tegel pers comm)
BTV0M002_LS	AD1419	AD1602	6.08	Batavia LS1 group 10 timbers (Daly et al 2021)
G330ZZ01	AD1380	AD1480	5.79	Bramsche 4 timbers (Göttingen Uni revised Daly 2007a)
G3120Z01	AD1388	AD1620	5.75	Bodenfelde 9 timbers (Göttingen Uni revised Daly 2007a)
DM200006	AD914	AD1873	5.71	Lüneburger Heide (Göttingen Uni)
meuse2	AD672	AD1989	5.70	MEUSE2 (Tegel pers comm)
NLC01Z01	AD1438	AD1528	5.67	Beltrum Netherlands 4 timbers (RING revised Daly 2007a)
liege1	AD709	AD1614	5.59	LIEGE1 (Tegel pers comm)
DM200005	AD915	AD1873	5.57	Niedersachsen Nord (Göttingen Uni)

Table 3. Myttingeviken, Stockholm. Result of the correlation between the tree-ring curve from plank sample p5 (Z2950059) from *Neptunus* and diverse site and master chronologies. The source of the chronologies is given. The grey tone highlights the high *t*-values.

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Filenames	-	-	Z295008a p11	
-	start	dates	AD1444	
-	dates	end	AD1537	
00651m08	AD1418	AD1597	6.49	Ship B&W1 lengthening 7 timbers (Daly 2007a)
TWWFMD01	AD1216	AD1660	6.24	NL Twente/Westfalen 51 trees (Dominguez Delmas unpubl)
G352DZ01	AD1433	AD1560	6.02	Kirchgellersen 2 timbers (Göttingen Uni revised Daly 2007a)
n1wf1040	AD1040	AD1972	5.72	Nederland. Westfalen (H.Tisje 1987 unpubl)
G340RZ01	AD1417	AD1588	5.51	Braunschweig 2 timbers (Göttingen Uni revised Daly 2007a)
G350RZ02	AD1394	AD1556	5.46	Celle 30 timbers (Göttingen Uni revised Daly 2007a)

Table 4. Myttingeviken, Stockholm. Result of the correlation between the tree-ring curve from frame sample p11 (Z295008a) from *Neptunus* and diverse site and master chronologies. The source of the chronologies is given. The grey tone highlights the high *t*-values.

Filenames	-	-	Z295010a p12	
-	start	dates	AD1545	
-	dates	end	AD1595	
H1178M01	AD1397	AD1624	5.20	Preetz Thiemenhaus + Klosterhof 19 timbers (Hamburg Uni revised Daly 2007a)
G331AZ01	AD1490	AD1614	5.18	Bückerburg 2 timbers (Göttingen Uni revised Daly 2007a)
G370YZ01	AD1510	AD1654	5.16	Jork 4 timbers (Göttingen Uni revised Daly 2007a)
Z1463M01	AD1445	AD1637	5.09	Raasepori Jussarö Finland frames 2 timbers (Daly 2015b)
00651m04	AD1386	AD1597	4.98	Cph B&W Vrag 1 (Daly 2007a)
G370HZ01	AD1426	AD1617	4.97	Oldenburg 31 timbers (Göttingen Uni revised Daly 2007a)
H1111M01	AD1478	AD1630	4.92	HL-Engelsgr.47 2 timbers (Hamburg Uni revised Daly 2007a)
DM200001	AD1082	AD1972	4.77	Nieders. Kuestenraum (Göttingen Uni)
H115CM01	AD1452	AD1674	4.75	Preetz Markt 24 9 timbers (Hamburg Uni revised Daly 2007a)

Table 5. Myttingeviken, Stockholm. Result of the correlation between the tree-ring curve from frame sample p12 (Z295010a) from *Neptunus* and diverse site and master chronologies. The source of the chronologies is given. The grey tone highlights the high *t*-values.

Filenames	-	-	Z2950069 p8	
-	start	dates	AD1519	
-	dates	end	AD1609	
G360GZ01	AD1508	AD1666	5.57	Donnerhorst 2 timbers (Göttingen Uni revised Daly 2007a)
G341CZ02	AD1455	AD1667	5.40	Wennigsen 8 timbers (Göttingen Uni revised Daly 2007a)
ntwe1357	AD1357	AD1724	5.18	NL Twente. (D.de Vries unpubl)
GO603Z02	AD1518	AD1583	5.08	Pabstorf 2 timbers (Göttingen Uni revised Daly 2007a)
n1wf1040	AD1040	AD1972	4.94	Nederland. Westfalen (H.Tisje 1987 unpubl)
G330LZ01	AD1436	AD1609	4.82	Bückerburg 12 timbers (Göttingen Uni revised Daly 2007a)
B027oak F g...	AD1529	AD1753	4.78	Gammel Strand Copenhagen oak F gr2 10 timbers (Daly 2016b)
P702101m	AD1476	AD1610	4.71	Poland Lubawa (Wazny pers comm)
GO602Z02	AD1515	AD1579	4.70	Pabstorf 4 timbers (Göttingen Uni revised Daly 2007a)

Table 6. Myttingeviken, Stockholm. Result of the correlation between the tree-ring curve from beam sample p8 (Z2950069) from *Neptunus* and diverse site and master chronologies. The source of the chronologies is given. The grey tone highlights the high *t*-values.

Filenames	-	-	Z295004a p4	
-	start	dates	AD1529	
-	dates	end	AD1609	
9M456781	109BC	AD1986	5.53	Jylland/Fyn (Nationalmuseet)
germ6	AD1376	AD1972	5.28	Oldenburg 138 timbers (Eckstein ITRDB)
H137HM01	AD1526	AD1652	5.13	Drage Westerstr. 2 timbers (Hamburg Uni revised Daly 2007a)
Z274M001	AD1524	AD1666	4.90	Gothenburg ships 3 timbers (Daly in prep)
DM200001	AD1082	AD1972	4.80	Nieders. Kuestenraum (Göttingen Uni)
Z277M001	AD1408	AD1705	4.76	Gothenburg ships wreck 2 4 timbers (Daly in prep)
CD60JZ01	AD1385	AD1652	4.24	Ulstrup 3 timbers (Nationalmuseet revised Daly 2007a)
Z044201A	AD1485	AD1608	4.23	Kanonvraget spantende x131 (Daly 2013c)
Z010002A	AD1480	AD1623	4.19	Larvik Norge ship x19 køl (Daly 2007b)
HO12IM01	AD1534	AD1613	4.09	Roduchelsdorf 4 timbers (Hamburg Uni revised Daly 2007a)
Z231M001	AD1420	AD1585	4.07	Resö Bohuslän 2 timbers (Daly 2018)

Table 7. Myttingeviken, Stockholm. Result of the correlation between the tree-ring curve from deck beam sample p4 (Z295004a) from *Neptunus* and diverse site and master chronologies. The source of the chronologies is given. The grey tone highlights the high *t*-values.

Filenames	-	-	Z2950029 p10	
-	start	dates	AD1470	
-	dates	end	AD1613	
G370LZ01	AD1505	AD1663	7.87	Zetel 3 timbers (Göttingen Uni revised Daly 2007a)
G370JZ01	AD1459	AD1584	6.35	Emden 2 timbers (Göttingen Uni revised Daly 2007a)
G370HZ01	AD1426	AD1617	6.34	Oldenburg 31 timbers (Göttingen Uni revised Daly 2007a)
DM200001	AD1082	AD1972	5.76	Nieders. Kuestenraum (Göttingen Uni)
H118TM01	AD1404	AD1605	5.56	Suelfeld Kirche 14 timbers (Hamburg Uni revised Daly 2007a)
G3743Z01	AD1506	AD1666	5.55	Esens 3 timbers (Göttingen Uni revised Daly 2007a)
G331DZ01	AD1518	AD1613	5.31	Bückeberg 3 timbers (Göttingen Uni revised Daly 2007a)
H1105M01	AD1437	AD1612	5.06	Moelln Hauptstr.107 2 timbers (Hamburg Uni revised Daly 2007a)
DM100006end	AD1330	AD1650	4.87	Lübeck (Hamburg Uni)
G330VZ01	AD1388	AD1589	4.80	Oldendorf Hessisch 7 timbers (Göttingen Uni revised Daly 2007a)
G3716Z01	AD1445	AD1661	4.75	Jork 3 timbers (Göttingen Uni revised Daly 2007a)
G360TZ01	AD1495	AD1676	4.66	Hassbergen 5 timbers (Göttingen Uni revised Daly 2007a)
G360YZ01	AD1458	AD1579	4.66	Bremen 6 timbers (Göttingen Uni revised Daly 2007a)

Table 8. Myttingeviken, Stockholm. Result of the correlation between the tree-ring curve from knee sample p10 (Z2950029) from *Neptunus* and diverse site and master chronologies. The source of the chronologies is given. The grey tone highlights the high *t*-values.

Filenames	-	-	Z295003a p1	
-	start	dates	AD1515	
-	dates	end	AD1628	
CD50PZ02	AD1458	AD1618	5.01	Varns Klokkehus 3 timbers (Nationalmuseet revised Daly 2007a)
DM100003	AD436	AD1968	4.44	Schleswig-Holstein (Hamburg Uni)
G370HZ01	AD1426	AD1617	4.28	Oldenburg 31 timbers (Göttingen Uni revised Daly 2007a)
H1374M01	AD1500	AD1617	4.28	Bargen Haus Erich 5 timbers (Hamburg Uni revised Daly 2007a)
G370LZ01	AD1505	AD1663	4.23	Zetel 3 timbers (Göttingen Uni revised Daly 2007a)
H11C0M01	AD1443	AD1613	4.15	Wahlstorf. Herrenha 6 timbers (Hamburg Uni revised Daly 2007a)
Z1080M02 ship2	AD1358	AD1618	4.14	Brünbüttel Ship Cuxhaven ship gr2 9 timbers (Daly 2014)
9M456781	109BC	AD1986	4.12	Jylland/Fyn (Nationalmuseet)

Table 9. Myttingeviken, Stockholm. Result of the correlation between the tree-ring curve from knee sample p1 (Z295003a) from *Neptunus* and diverse site and master chronologies. The source of the chronologies is given. The grey tone highlights the high *t*-values.

Tu Löver

Tu Löver belonged to the Danish Navy and was captured by the Swedes in 1644 (Glete 2010), so she must have been completed before this event. Glete lists *Tu Löver* as converted to a fireship in 1658.

Six samples are from *Tu Löver*, all oak (*Quercus* sp.). Five of the samples are dated.

One sample P18 (Z296006a) is from a wale. It contains 99 tree-rings, all heartwood. This sample is from a tree felled after AD 1554.

One sample P13 (Z296002a) is from a frame. It contains 237 tree-rings, all heartwood, but the sample is preserved to the heartwood/sapwood boundary. This sample is from a tree felled AD 1607-22.

Two samples are from hull planks. P16 (Z2960059) contains 94 tree-rings, all heartwood. It is from a tree felled after AD 1559. P15 (Z2960019) contains 107 tree-rings all heartwood. This sample is from a tree felled after AD 1610.

One sample P19 (Z296004a) is from a gunwale. It contains 156 tree-rings, all heartwood. It is from a tree felled after AD 1608.

Finally, one sample, P14 (Z296003a) from a frame, contains 89 tree-rings of which six are sapwood rings. This sample could not be dated.

If it is assumed that all trees from *Tu Löver* were felled at the same time, then this felling took place around AD 1608-22 (indicated with orange shading in fig. 1).

Provenance *Tu Löver*

The dated samples from *Tu Löver* do not correlate significantly with each other (table 1). Thus, these five samples are dated independently. The correlations between each tree-ring curve from *Tu Löver* with a range of tree-ring datasets for Northern Europe are shown in tables 10 to 14 below.

Some timbers correlate best with northern German datasets while others are dating with southern Scandinavia. The gunwale timber is dating with southern Norway and, perhaps coincidentally, with the three dated timbers from the wreck at Fehmarn, identified as '*Delmenhorst*', a Danish vessel which was lost during the Battle of Fehmarn. The heterogeneity of the timber used in this ship reflects the diverse sources for timber that were exploited in the early 17th century.

Finally, one sample (P17) is from a post found in association with *Tu Löver*. It is *Picea* sp./*Larix* sp., spruce/larch and contains just 36 tree-rings. This sample is not analysed further.

Filenames	-	-	Z296006a p18	
-	start	dates	AD1440	
-	dates	end	AD1538	
HO14ZM01	AD1387	AD1661	5.92	Gadebusch Schloss 17 timbers (Hamburg Uni revised Daly 2007a)
H1178M01	AD1397	AD1624	5.43	Preetz Thiemenhaus + Klosterhof 19 timbers (Hamburg Uni revised Daly 2007a)
Z093M001	AD1420	AD1614	5.33	Vasa barrels 7 timbers (Daly 2013a)
H11KPM01	AD1422	AD1557	5.32	HL Mengstrasse 23 3 timbers (Hamburg Uni revised Daly 2007a)
E_German	AD1343	AD1968	5.27	East Germany Climate project sites 339 timbers (Daly unpubl)
H11H6M01	AD1391	AD1544	5.27	HL Gr.Petersgrube 18 timbers (Hamburg Uni revised Daly 2007a)
005400m8	AD1374	AD1592	5.22	Bredfjed ship (Bartholin pers comm)
Z174M001	AD1383	AD1571	5.08	Hillerød latrine 3 timbers (Daly 2016c)
H11ISM01	AD1389	AD1563	5.07	HL Alfstrasse 38 9 timbers (Hamburg Uni revised Daly 2007a)
F042M001	AD1360	AD1621	5.04	Nørregade 12 Horsens v2 3 timbers (Daly 2019a)
H11EGM01	AD1391	AD1658	5.02	Ahrensburg Schloss 7 timbers (Hamburg Uni revised Daly 2007a)
H11GSM01	AD1397	AD1543	5.00	HL Engelsgrube 31 8 timbers (Hamburg Uni revised Daly 2007a)
H1177M01	AD1424	AD1585	4.91	Preetz Klosterh. 19. 8 timbers (Hamburg Uni revised Daly 2007a)
GO10ZZ01	AD1470	AD1677	4.88	Güstrow 7 timbers (Göttingen Uni revised Daly 2007a)
H11IWM01	AD1389	AD1571	4.82	HL Gr.Petersgrube 29 15 timbers (Hamburg Uni revised Daly 2007a)
Z0309M01	AD1395	AD1561	4.82	Barcode Oslo ship BC09 2 timbers (Daly 2010)

Table 10. Myttingeviken, Stockholm. Result of the correlation between the tree-ring curve from wale sample p18 (Z296006a) from *Tu Löver* and diverse site and master chronologies. The source of the chronologies is given. The grey tone highlights the high t -values.

Filenames	-	-	Z296002a p13	
-	start	dates	AD1356	
-	dates	end	AD1592	
Z249M001	AD1375	AD1588	7.27	Bispevika 16 Oslo 2 timbers (Daly 2019b)
6094M002	AD1450	AD1660	6.12	Funder kirke later material 4 timbers (Daly 2002)
Z040M001	AD1386	AD1567	6.06	Gåsehage Randers 2 timbers (Daly 2009)
Z274M001	AD1524	AD1666	5.71	Gothenburg ships 3 timbers (Daly in prep)
00652M02	AD1405	AD1607	5.65	B&W Grund Vrag 2. 2 trees (Daly 1997b)
G311LZ01	AD1386	AD1759	5.45	Hemeln 11 timbers (Göttingen Uni revised Daly 2007a)
EP41592	AD1390	AD1592	5.45	Stirling Castle Scotland episode 4 (Crone pers comm)
B027oak C o...	AD1331	AD1557	5.43	Gammel Strand Copenhagen C orange 23 timbers (Daly 2016b)
WSshipsM01	AD1352	AD1636	5.38	West Swedish ships 29 timbers (Daly unpubl)
NB700000	AD1345	AD1538	5.25	Helsingør (Nationalmuseet)
H011M001	AD1386	AD1563	5.17	Aalborg Algade Tiendeladen hus 4 timbers (Daly 2016a)
2x900001	AD830	AD1997	5.09	Sjælland Denmark 227 timbers (Nationalmuseet)
E014M001 oak6	AD1242	AD1503	5.09	Slotsvej Gram dæmning oak 50 timbers (Daly 2015a)
q415029m04	AD1356	AD1540	5.08	Evangelistas altarpiece Seville Cathedral 29 planks (Rodríguez-Trobajo & Domínguez-Delmás 2015)
WSwedM25	AD1344	AD1560	5.04	West Sweden 49 timbers (Daly unpubl)
SScanM25	AD1343	AD1548	4.94	Southern Scandinavia 36 timbers (Daly unpubl)
Z089m001	AD1399	AD1581	4.86	Oslo Barcode skib 5 9 timbers (Daly 2013b)

Table 11. Myttingeviken, Stockholm. Result of the correlation between the tree-ring curve from frame sample p13 (Z296002a) from *Tu Löver* and diverse site and master chronologies. The source of the chronologies is given. The grey tone highlights the high *t*-values.

Filenames	-	-	Z2960059 p16	
-	start	dates	AD1450	
-	dates	end	AD1543	
2121M002	AD1052	AD1596	7.66	Suså Næstved all posts (Daly 2001)
SScanM25	AD1343	AD1548	7.05	Southern Scandinavia 36 timbers (Daly unpubl)
B027oak B	AD1248	AD1532	6.88	Gammel Strand Copenhagen B purple 21 timbers (Daly 2016b)
ZEALAND0	AD452	AD1770	6.82	Sjælland Denmark 249 timbers (Daly unpubl)
B037M001	AD1337	AD1550	6.71	Favrholm Mølle 20 timbers (Daly 2016d)
Ep3mnall	AD1361	AD1539	6.68	Stirling Castle Scotland (Crone pers comm)
Z146M002	AD1445	AD1691	6.59	Raasepori Jussarö Finland frames 3 timbers (Daly 2015b)
SM000005	AD1274	AD1974	6.56	Skåne Blekinge (Lund University)
Z027M002	AD1313	AD1567	6.50	Amager Strand ship 9 timbers (Daly 2008)
midtjy17	AD536	AD1980	6.16	Mid Jutland (Christensen pers comm)
B028M003	AD1386	AD1576	5.99	Køge Havn 4 timbers (Daly 2013d)
WSwedM25	AD1344	AD1560	5.94	West Sweden 49 timbers (Daly unpubl)
CD60NZ01	AD1377	AD1576	5.90	Skaføgård 12 timbers (Nationalmuseet revised Daly 2007a)
702800M3	AD1353	AD1515	5.77	Mejrup kirke (Bartholin 1997)
D0137M04	AD1286	AD1520	5.63	Thomas B Thriges 12 timbers (Daly & Daly 2019)

Table 12. Myttingeviken, Stockholm. Result of the correlation between the tree-ring curve from plank sample p16 (Z2960059) from *Tu Löver* and diverse site and master chronologies. The source of the chronologies is given. The grey tone highlights the high *t*-values.

Filenames	-	-	Z2960019 p15	
-	start	dates	AD1488	
-	dates	end	AD1594	
H11EGM01	AD1391	AD1658	7.01	Ahrensburg Schloss 7 timbers (Hamburg Uni revised Daly 2007a)
H118TM01	AD1404	AD1605	6.22	Suelfeld Kirche 14 timbers (Hamburg Uni revised Daly 2007a)
H129JM01	AD1449	AD1616	6.10	Jersbek 9 timbers (Hamburg Uni revised Daly 2007a)
H11ABM01	AD1494	AD1660	5.88	Eutin am Markt 10 3 timbers (Hamburg Uni revised Daly 2007a)
G3716Z01	AD1445	AD1661	5.80	Jork 3 timbers (Göttingen Uni revised Daly 2007a)
G370KZ01	AD1428	AD1643	5.61	Jork 4 timbers (Göttingen Uni revised Daly 2007a)
H125OM01	AD1529	AD1656	5.52	Horst Hinterm Holz 1. 2 timbers (Hamburg Uni revised Daly 2007a)
H112SM01	AD1423	AD1588	5.48	Linau Hauptstr. 35 3 timbers (Hamburg Uni revised Daly 2007a)
DM100007	AD1080	AD1967	5.34	Hamburg (Hamburg Uni)
DM100008	AD457	AD1723	5.34	Lübeck (Hamburg Uni)
H111MM01	AD1458	AD1605	5.34	Lauenburg Elbstras 14 timbers (Hamburg Uni revised Daly 2007a)
DM200001	AD1082	AD1972	5.22	Nieders. Kuestenraum (Göttingen Uni)
G311UZ01	AD1372	AD1590	5.21	Einbeck 7 timbers (Göttingen Uni revised Daly 2007a)
H112TM01	AD1379	AD1610	5.19	Schiphorst Hauptstr 4 timbers (Hamburg Uni revised Daly 2007a)
G3719Z01	AD1393	AD1613	5.11	Jork 6 timbers (Göttingen Uni revised Daly 2007a)
Z270M002	AD1482	AD1598	5.02	Vaxholm Stockholm Vrak 1 2 timbers (Daly 2020a)
G330JZ01	AD1365	AD1585	4.90	Stadthagen 5 timbers (Göttingen Uni revised Daly 2007a)

Table 13. Myttingeviken, Stockholm. Result of the correlation between the tree-ring curve from plank sample p15 (Z2960019) from *Tu Löver* and diverse site and master chronologies. The source of the chronologies is given. The grey tone highlights the high *t*-values.

Filenames	-	-	Z296004a p19	
-	start	dates	AD1445	
-	dates	end	AD1600	
DCCDnorway	AD1248	AD1648	8.87	Norway 192 timbers (Daly unpubl)
21015M02	AD1305	AD1743	7.68	Copenhagen B&W Grund 24 trees (Daly 1997a&c)
Z071m004	AD1304	AD1595	6.28	Oslo Barcode BC08 5 timbers (Daly 2011c)
FTMAS2	AD1318	AD1572	6.27	Fenton Tower Scotland IMPORTS 5 timbers (Crone pers comm)
N053N027	AD1480	AD1678	5.83	Vennesla and Bjorvatn Norway (Christensen pers comm)
Z280M001	AD1362	AD1564	5.76	Femern 'Delmenhorst' 3 timbers (Daly 2020b)
B027oak F g...	AD1413	AD1689	5.68	Gammel Strand oak F green gr1 2 timbers (Daly 2016b)
Z059m001	AD1371	AD1659	5.46	Klim Strandvraget 2 timbers (Daly 2011a)
Z065M001	AD1355	AD1600	5.30	Bjørvika Kenneth Oslo 2 timbers (Daly 2011b)
CARNCKx8	AD1317	AD1588	4.82	Carnock Castle Scotland IMPORTS (Crone pers comm)

Table 14. Myttingeviken, Stockholm. Result of the correlation between the tree-ring curve from gunwale sample p19 (Z296004a) from *Tu Löver* and diverse site and master chronologies. The source of the chronologies is given. The grey tone highlights the high *t*-values.

Identification of the ships through dendrochronology?

It has frequently been demonstrated that acquisition of timber for shipbuilding in Northern Europe, by the 17th century, is a complicated endeavour. *Batavia*, a ship built in Amsterdam in 1628, by the Dutch East India Company, that wrecked on her first voyage off the Western Australian coast, has been shown to have been built of timber from at least three widely different sources (Daly et al 2021). This is perhaps not so surprising, as the Low Countries suffered from timber shortage much earlier. It is more surprising that *Vasa*, built in Stockholm in the same year as *Batavia*, was also built of timber from a variety of sources. Sweden had its own timber resources, including availability of large oak trees, but nevertheless imported timber from the eastern Baltic region and from further afield (Daly 2021). The same pattern of timber transport is also apparent in the Danish region. Timbers for waterfront structures in Copenhagen, from the early and mid-16th centuries, were sourced on the Swedish side of the Øresund, which was still under the Danish Crown. By the mid 17th century, Denmark was using Norwegian timber sources for similar building needs (Daly 2016b).

How then do the dendrochronological results in this analysis help to confirm or disprove whether the two ships at Myttingeviken indeed are the remains of the Danish-owned ships, *Neptunus* and *Tu Löver*, captured at the Battle of Fehmarn? In terms of their chronology, *Neptunus* and *Tu Löver* were taken by the Swedish Navy in 1644. The dendrochronology demonstrates that the trees for the two wrecks were felled around 1629-1636 for *Neptunus*, and around 1608-1622 for *Tu Löver*. So in terms of their chronology, these two wrecks clearly represent ships built before 1644.

In terms of the region of origin of the timber used for these ships, the results are not as clear-cut. Diverse timber sources were utilised for both ships. The five dated timbers from *Tu Löver* suggest that it was built from timbers from Southern Scandinavia and northern Germany, which would fit very well with a ship built in Denmark. *Neptunus* timbers indicate that timber was also sourced further westwards towards The Low Countries, but again, sources closer to Denmark seem also to have been exploited. It would be very interesting to discover if there are records for where the two ships had been built, and compare this information with the dendrochronological results. Standing alone, the dendroprovenance results in this analysis cannot identify the building locations of the two wrecks found at Myttingeviken.

Methodology

Measuring and analysis of the material is carried out using the program "DENDRO" (Tyers, 1997) in which the calculation of the *t*-value ("t-test") "CROS" (Baillie & Pilcher, 1973) is embedded. For estimating the felling date for the oak in this analysis, the sapwood statistic for Northern Germany (ca. 20 sapwood years (-5+10) (Hollstein 1980)) is used. However a different sapwood statistic is used for one sample, P19. For this the shorter estimate for Southern Norway (c. 15 sapwood years (-8+6)) (Christensen & Havemann 1998) is more appropriate. In the analysis master and site chronologies for Northern Europe are consulted.

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Catalogue

filename	sample title and number, species	rings	start yr.	end yr.	pith	sapwood	bark?	conversion	extra end	ave ring width mm	interpretation / felling
Mytingeviken, Stockholm 'Neptunus'											
Z2950019	Mytingeviken Neptunus p3 bordläggning QUSP	79	AD 1456	AD 1534	G	0	N	T	H1	1,68	after AD 1550
Z2950029	Mytingeviken Neptunus p10 knä QUSP	144	AD 1470	AD 1613	C	4	N	O	S1	0,68	AD 1624-39
Z295003a	Mytingeviken Neptunus p1 knä QUSP	114	AD 1515	AD 1628	G	22	N	Q	S1	1,31	AD 1629-36
Z295004a	Mytingeviken Neptunus p4 däcksbalk QUSP	81	AD 1529	AD 1609	G	0	N	O	N	1,85	after AD 1624
Z2950059	Mytingeviken Neptunus p5 bordläggning QUSP	129	AD 1411	AD 1539	G	0	N	T	H1	1,33	after AD 1555
Z2950069	Mytingeviken Neptunus p8 häckbalk QUSP	91	AD 1519	AD 1609	F	0	N	O	H1	1,37	after AD 1625
Z295007a	Mytingeviken Neptunus p6 däcksbalk QUSP	65			V	0	N	O	H1	4,14	undated
Z295008a	Mytingeviken Neptunus p11 spant QUSP	94	AD 1444	AD 1537	G	0	N	O	H1	1,28	after AD 1553
Z295009a	Mytingeviken Neptunus p7 spant QUSP	62			C	4	N	O	N	2,02	undated
Z295010a	Mytingeviken Neptunus p12 spant QUSP	51	AD 1545	AD 1595	C	0	N	O	H1	1,91	after AD 1611
Z295011a	Mytingeviken Neptunus p9 plank QUSP	53			G	0	N	T	H1	2,75	undated
Z295101a	Mytingeviken Neptunus p2 påle PISY	53			C	20	N	S	S1	1,51	undated
Conversion: R = radial split plank, T = tangential plank, W = whole timber, S = squared whole timber, H = half timber, Q = quarter timber, O = other conversion. Pith: C = centre, V = less than 5 rings, F = 5 – 10 rings, G = greater than 10 rings. QUSP = <i>Quercus sp.</i> , oak. PISY = <i>Pinus sp.</i> , pine. PCAB = <i>Picea sp./Larix sp.</i> , spruce/larch											
Aoife Daly, Ph.D.				11th November 2021							

filename	sample title and number, species	rings	start yr.	end yr.	pith	sapwood	bark?	conversion	extra end	ave ring width mm	interpretation / felling
Mytingeviken, Stockholm 'Tu Löver'											
Z2960019	Mytingeviken Tu Löver p15 bordläggning QUSP	107	AD 1488	AD 1594	C	0	N	T	H1	1,56	after AD 1610
Z296002a	Mytingeviken Tu Löver p13 spant QUSP	237	AD 1356	AD 1592	C	H/S	N	O	N	0,82	AD 1607-22
Z296003a	Mytingeviken Tu Löver p14 spant QUSP	89			G	6	N	O	S1	2,94	undated
Z296004a	Mytingeviken Tu Löver p19 vaterbord QUSP	156	AD 1445	AD 1600	G	0	N	O	H1	0,86	after AD 1608
Z2960059	Mytingeviken Tu Löver p16 bordläggning QUSP	94	AD 1450	AD 1543	G	0	N	T	H1	1,25	after AD 1559
Z296006a	Mytingeviken Tu Löver p18 berghult QUSP	99	AD 1440	AD 1538	G	0	N	O	H1	1,97	after AD 1554
	Mytingeviken Tu Löver p17 påle PCAB	36									
Conversion: R = radial split plank, T = tangential plank, W = whole timber, S = squared whole timber, H = half timber, Q = quarter timber, O = other conversion. Pith: C = centre, V = less than 5 rings, F = 5 – 10 rings, G = greater than 10 rings. QUSP = <i>Quercus sp.</i> , oak. PISY = <i>Pinus sp.</i> , pine. PCAB = <i>Picea sp./Larix sp.</i> , spruce/larch											
Aoife Daly, Ph.D.				11th November 2021							